

Assessment Report

31 May 2011

Introduction

NESCent promotes the synthesis of information, concepts and knowledge to address significant, emerging, or novel questions in evolutionary science and its applications. NESCent achieves this by supporting research and education across disciplinary, institutional, geographic, and demographic boundaries.

NESCent's assessment program is divided into three evaluative tiers. Specifically we seek to evaluate whether:

1. NESCent supports research and education across disciplinary, institutional, geographic, and demographic boundaries.
2. NESCent scientists are addressing questions that are significant, emerging, or novel in evolutionary science.
3. NESCent accomplishes (2) by promoting the synthesis of information, concepts and knowledge.

These questions define our three tiers of assessment, and can be simplified into (1) people, (2) products, and (3) process.

The **first tier of assessment** includes systematically tracking aspects of participants and activities at the center and comparing these measures against specified benchmarks. For example, we track applications received and supported, disciplinary fields and demographics of applicants and participants, meetings held, etc., in order to understand how our day-to-day activities are meeting the goals of the center. A few examples of such goals are: to receive and support applications from the full range of disciplines and sub-disciplines in evolutionary science; to ensure that our supported scientists are geographically, ethnically racially and career-stage diverse; and to ensure that the number of females is at minimum representative of potential applicant pools.

The **second tier of assessment** is analysis of products resulting from NESCent activities in order to understand the broader impact of NESCent-sponsored activities on individuals and the greater scientific community.

The **third tier of assessment** is formative analysis, the results of which can be used to improve the ways that the center promotes synthetic evolutionary science. The focus is on process and examples include: analyses of the behaviors and attitudes of scientists towards collaboration, how such behavior is changed as a result of NESCent support, and how participant demographics may influence productivity. The core of the third tier is the “Science of Science” project in conjunction with Jonathon Cummings, Ph.D. (Associate Professor of Management) from the Fuqua School of Business at Duke University.

A majority of data needed for assessment is collected in the internal NESCent Administrative Database (NEAD) that serves as the backbone for all the center’s evaluative activities. The strength of NEAD rests on the routine use and accumulation of data from multiple users from center Directors and administrative staff to individual participants in NESCent activities. Almost all aspects of NESCent’s day-to-day operations, e.g. registering for meeting, proposal process, updating the website, require utilizing our web-based interface of NEAD. This allows us to collect a wide range of data needed for assessment activities with an automated process. For example, we have demographic data on nearly 100% of participants in center activities.

Tier 1

1. *Does NESCent continue to attract new participants into the center?*

Central to our mission is the continued attraction of scientists previously unaffiliated with the center into NESCent activities. This will ensure a continued flux of novel and diverse ideas, approaches, and backgrounds into NESCent.

Figure 1: Cumulative total and new visitors at NESCent from center's start date to January 2011

Since the center's inception the total number of visitors continues to grow (Figure 1 left) with no signal of leveling or diminishing (purple line, $p < 0.0001$, $R^2 = 0.986$). In addition, NESCent continues to consistently attract new scientists into the center (Figure 1 right; $p < 0.0001$, $R^2 = 0.989$). **Annually, ~54% of participants in NESCent activities are new to the center.**

2. *Has NESCent increased the number of supported science activities?*

With an increase in NSF support in the second funding cycle, NESCent has increased the number of supported activities (Figure 2). We have increased the number of catalysis meetings from a daily mean of 3-4 active meetings to 7-9 active meetings (an active meeting is one which remains in our database until it has been completed). Equally, the number of active working groups has increased recently from a daily average of 10-11 to 16 groups. We are also maintaining our peak postdoctoral and sabbatical community with 17 resident scientists. The first round of 2011 seeks to expand this community to 19 total.

Figure 2 Top: Number of active projects by type per day from the center’s start date to 3/1/11. **Bottom:** Number of total active projects from the center’s start date to 3/1/11.

3. How diverse is NESCent in participant disciplines, institutions, geography, demography and career stage?

3.1 Disciplines

NESCent's goal is to continuously draw upon a broad diversity of participants that span multiple backgrounds to tackle the broad assortment of outstanding questions in evolutionary science. Whether examining how participants self-describe their disciplinary backgrounds (Figure 3) or how principal investigators categorize their NESCent supported projects (Figure 4), **NESCent appears to be incorporating a diverse set of disciplines into our portfolio.** Beyond our strength in areas typically associated with evolutionary science, e.g. systematics and ecology, NESCent's portfolio also includes representation among non-biological sciences. Nearly 25% of our participants associate themselves with non-biological disciplines (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Self-reported representation among fields of NESCent participants

Figure 4: Number of projects among 14 disciplinary categories as reported by principal investigators.

3.2 Institutions

Figure 5: Home institution type for all NESCent participants since center's start

Although most NESCent participants are from doctorate-granting institutions (Figure 5), **24% of participants encompass a broad set of institution types** ranging from primary education to associate/baccalaureate colleges and universities; these also include non-academic research settings, e.g. NGO's, government organizations, and museums.

Figure 6: Home country for all NESCent participants since center's start. Black corresponds to greater participants and light grey to few participants. Green areas are areas with no representation.

NESCent is a national center with an international reach. **Over years 1-6 of the center, participants have represented 50 countries from every inhabited continent** (Figure 6). Nonetheless, Indonesia/Southeast Asia, Africa, the Middle East, and Eastern Europe remain areas with poor representation.

3.3 *Minority Representation*

Figure 7: Minority representation at NESCent per project type since the center's start. Three comparison groups are given (far right columns) of all receiving doctorates in biology in 2008, all Ph.D.'s in science in 2006, and Ph.D.'s in biological sciences in 2008. Comparison data are from NSF (<http://www.nsf.gov/statistics/showpub.cfm?TopID=2&SubID=27>).

Minority representation varies considerably among programs at NESCent (Figure 7). Our graduate and sabbatical programs have been almost exclusively represented by Caucasians. Hispanics and Latinos are only represented in our postdoctoral program, Asians only in our catalysis and working group meetings, and African Americans only in working groups. Overall, minority representation at NESCent (11%) is below demographics for all Ph.D.'s in biology in NSF (23%). **Minority representation among NESCent's advisory board, currently composed of 17 scientists from the evolutionary sciences, is 34%, higher than the NSF comparison statistics (Figure 8).** It is unclear whether NESCent's low numbers reflect a trend mirroring evolutionary biology as a whole, for which there is currently no data. Clearly, a concerted effort is required to attract minorities into NESCent programs.

Figure 8: Minority representation among current NESCent Advisory Board members

3.4 Gender Representation

NESCent programs on average have 30% female representation both in terms of PIs and participants (Figure 9, top). Also, in all but one year, 2006, NESCent has offered a greater percentage of postdoctoral fellowships to females than represented in our applicant pool (Figure 9, bottom).

Figure 9 Top: Percentage of female applicants in postdoctoral fellowship program (dark orange) versus percentage of female participants offered fellowship (light orange). Bottom: Gender representation of principal investigators and participants in NESCent supported programs. Comparison is shown with NSF statistics of practicing Ph.D.'s in biology. (NSF data from <http://www.nsf.gov/statistics/showpub.cfm?TopID=2&SubID=45>)

3.5 Career Stage

NESCent seeks to incorporate scientists from a variety of career stages in our programs. Incorporation of early career scientists provides valuable opportunities for networking and professional development. A mix of career stages can infuse energy and enthusiasm into meetings and activities. **A variety of career stages are represented among NESCent-affiliated scientists with fairly equal representation (Figure 10). Indeed, our representation among emerging (non-tenured scientists) and experienced scientists is remarkably even (Figure 11).**

Figure 10: Reported professions of all NESCent participants since the center's start

Figure 11: Representation of emerging (non-tenured) and experienced (tenured) scientists among all NESCent participants since the center's start

Tier 2

4. Does published research from NESCent supported projects span across multiple disciplines?

One of the modes of synthesis is linking concepts, data, and theory from disparate disciplines to produce novel outcomes. To what extent is this goal of multidisplinarity realized in NESCent products? Collaborating with visualization and scientometric expert Katy Börner (Indiana University), we charted NESCent publications onto a map of science. Groups of journals characterizing the disciplines on the map were defined using a metric based on a combination of the bibliographic coupling of references and keyword vectors. A three-dimensional layout of the disciplines (groups of journals, denoted by text and colors in Figure 12) places those disciplines on a sphere, which is then unfolded using a mercator projection to give a two-dimensional version of the map. Research specialties (gray open circles) were also defined. NESCent-published research was overlaid onto this map based on discipline (colored open circles) and scaled to frequency of occurrence. **Of 13 disciplines and 554 research specialties in science, NESCent is represented in 12 and 144, respectively.**

Figure 12: Map of science. Colors denote the 13 major disciplines of science with open gray circles denoting research specialties. NESCent representation in the map, based on journal of publication, is indicated by the scaled (based on publication frequency) colored circles. Map from the Cyberinfrastructure for Network Science Center at Indiana University. Copyright© 2008 The Regents of the University of California

We also complement this with a more fine-grained analysis based on the content of the papers as opposed to where they are published. Using the NESCent publications that occur in ISI Web of Knowledge, we retrieved their subject categories. A single paper may have multiple subject categories. We compared this to a selected group of randomly chosen NSF-funded publications in evolutionary biology from the same publication time span. **NESCent publications (categories: n=28) covered approximately three times the subject categories than the comparison group (categories: n=10). NESCent publications**

are also more evenly distributed among categories than the comparison group (Figure 13). In the comparison group, 88% of the publications fall into just 4 categories. In contrast, 88% of NESCent publications fall into 10 subject categories. **Overall, we find that NESCent publications traverse a range of disciplines incorporating much more than just evolutionary biology.**

Figure 13: Representation of NESCent (blue) and comparison group (orange, see text) of published research among subject categories

5. Does published research from NESCent continue to transform?

For any research institute, a challenge is to continuously gain fresh perspectives and produce novel work. Has NESCent continued to shift research focus or has the center contributed only to a single research area? Collaborating with Chaomei Chen (Drexel University), we are developing a co-citation network of NESCent publications. Briefly, this analysis develops a network based on the mutual citations of papers in the analysis. The network indicates subject areas and can detail shifts in research focus. Our preliminary analysis indicates that **NESCent-published research has clearly shifted focus since the center’s start (Figure 14)**. Earlier work (cool colors) appears to have focused more on genetic and phylogenetic research. Later work (warm colors) appears to concentrate more on the application of genetic and phylogenetic frameworks to other research areas. This shift was gradual and linked to previous work as demonstrated by the fact that each year’s papers occur next to and link to the pre- or

proceeding year's work. Future questions will include whether the co-citation network as expanded and developing a comparison groups.

Figure 14: Co-citation map of NESCent publications from years 2006-2010 (represented by colors). Individual points represent papers cited by NESCent papers. Larger points denote papers more heavily cited by NESCent publications. Linkages between papers represent their shared citations. Disjunct clusters of co-citations indicate distinctive knowledge domains and largely insular citation networks.

6. *Are NESCent publications highly cited?*

A central question addressed by the NESCent assessment team is whether the center engages in significant, emerging, or novel questions in evolutionary science. One method of determining NESCent's significance in the field is by analyzing the impact of NESCent-sponsored publications as measured by citation patterns. NESCent's basic citation information is shown below (Figure 15).

In order to compare NESCent-published research against an appropriate comparison set of publications, a same-journal, same-issue companion set of papers was analyzed. For each NESCent-affiliated

publication, a companion paper of the same article type (review, commentary, research article, etc.) was randomly selected from the same issue of the same journal. In cases where this was impossible (for example, when the NESCent publication was the only item of its type in a particular issue), a companion paper was selected from the previous issue of the same journal, or from issues farther back in time if there was no suitable companion piece in the previous issue.

Figure 15: NESCent citation profile. Histogram shows frequency of citation counts for NESCent-published research; inset graph shows cumulative percentages by total citation count.

According to a Wilcoxon Related Samples Signed-Ranks test, **NESCent-affiliated publications (Mean=13.65, Median = 4.00) were cited significantly more frequently than papers in the same journal, same issue (SJSI) set (Mean = 10.21, Median = 3.00).** Of the 260 sets of paired items, NESCent papers were more frequently cited 128 times (49.23%), the papers had equal citation counts 52 times (20.00%), and the same journal, same issue paper was more frequently cited 81 times (31.15%). **NESCent papers were also less likely to be uncited than papers in the comparison set**, with 18.08% of NESCent papers uncited compared to 23.08% of the SJSI papers.

Similar citation analyses have been run using individual universities and broad disciplines as comparison groups. Using ISI, the top 40 research universities in terms of money spent on R&D, according to NSF figures, were each searched for items published between 2006 and 2010. Those search results were narrowed into three subsets: a) papers which were tagged with any of six evolution-related keywords; b) papers from that university which were funded by NSF; and c) papers from that university which were tagged with Evolutionary Biology. **The results showed that when compared with most universities, regardless of how the searches were limited, NESCent has a higher citation per item rate and a lower percent uncited rate (Figure 16).** Only five universities had a higher average citation rate than

NESCent in any of the three limiting scenarios, and no university's average citation count for NSF-funded publications exceeded NESCent's average.

Figure 16: Average Citations Per Evolutionary Biology Paper for NESCent (black) compared to other universities.

Finally, we wanted to address the question of how NESCent-published research compares to the broad field of evolutionary biology in terms of citation counts. To accomplish this, ISI was used to search for any items published between 2006 and 2010 within the topic of “evolution” and the subject category “Evolutionary Biology.” This search returned 5,881 publications. **NESCent-affiliated research (M = 13.65) is significantly more frequently cited than this broad disciplinary paper set (M = 2.91, $p < .001$).** Future research in this area will look to control for differences in the number of authors among institutions.

Tier 3

7. Do NESCent products reflect greater collaboration within supported projects?

Central to NESCent’s mission is constructing a culture and community of collaboration and integration among disciplines. Although catalysis meetings, working groups, and the in-house community are created to ensure interactions among scientists, these may not translate into truly synthetic products. For example, a publication may reflect a small subset of scientists from the total group who are more comfortable with collaboration. We examined this idea by looking at the number of authors and affiliations among papers on NESCent-related and non-related publications (Figure 16). The comparison group used for this analysis was the Same Journal, Same Issue set detailed above. **The analyses indicate that NESCent papers contain on average a greater number of authors (paired t-test, $p=0.0134$) and affiliations (paired t-test, $p<0.0001$).** NESCent papers on average typically possess at least one more author, 25% possess at least 5 more authors, and 5% are likely to contain 10% more authors than a ‘typical paper’. **NESCent publications are on average likely to contain twice as many affiliations as our comparison group.** The maximum number of affiliations of the comparison group is 11 while over 10% of NESCent’s publications contain over 11 affiliations. **These data suggests that NESCent provides a conducive environment for collaborations amongst scientists.**

Figure 17: Number of affiliations and authors on publications from NESCent (blue) and papers randomly drawn from the same journal and issue (orange)

8. *Are NESCent postdoctoral fellows more collaborative across a wider array of disciplines?*

The NESCent postdoctoral program represents a unique situation where fellows working on independent projects without formal research mentors are encouraged to collaborate with other fellows, visiting scientists at the center, and scientists from the broader community.

To examine the degree of collaboration, NSF Bioinformatics Fellows with research in evolutionary biology and high-ranking NESCent applicants that were declined due to limited availability in the program or declined an offer from NESCent were chosen as comparison groups. Both of these were considered valid comparisons to standardize for differences in research quality of fellows. Lists of Bioinformatics Fellows with research in evolutionary biology and declined NESCent applicants were used in ISI author searches to create sets of papers published by these authors after a critical date. The critical date was determined by the Fellows' start dates (in the case of the Bioinformatics Fellows) or the applicant's decline date. As individual bibliometrics possess both strengths and weaknesses, a variety of metrics were utilized to quantify both impact and collaboration among postdoctoral fellows. Using a principal components analysis these metrics were reduced to orthogonal axes corresponding uniquely to an axis of impact (PC 1) and an axis of collaboration (PC 2). The first two axes of the PCA accounted for 89% of the variation in the data (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Factor loadings on principal competent 1 and 2. Note that Factor 1 corresponds largely with impact metrics and Factor 2 with collaboration metrics

In terms of impact, Bioinformatics Fellows on average had higher scientific impact as measured by average number of citations, maximum number of citations, average journal impact factor, H-index, etc.

than either NESCent Fellows (t-test, $p=0.0130$) or NESCent Declined Applicants (t-test, $p=0.0049$). **However, in terms of collaboration, as measured by number of authors, departments, departmental types, etc., NESCent Fellows were higher than either NSF Bioinformatics Fellows (t-test, $p=0.0231$) or NESCent Declined Applicants (t-test, 0.0485) (Figure 19).** We also found that NESCent postdoctoral fellows tended to be closer to the first author position than NSF Bioinformatics Fellows. For example, 7 of the 9 most frequently cited NESCent Fellows occurred in the first or second author position on the highly cited paper. In contrast, the top five most frequently cited NSF Bioinformatics Fellows were 4th authors or lower.

Figure 19: Boxplots of scores of Postdoctoral Fellows on Factor 1 and Factor 2 among the three groups.

9. *What factors promote productivity within working groups?*

Productivity can vary substantially among working groups (0-25 publications, 0-5 software/ databases). Unlocking the processes that underlie this variation is vital for NESCent's success. Such information could be utilized in internal policy decisions and to guide principal investigators and working groups toward more productive strategies. As an initial project we examined whether the demographic makeup determined a working group's productivity as measured by the number of papers, databases, and software. We collected data for 29 working groups from our center's start on percentage of participants who were minorities, female, international, and emerging scientists, i.e. non-tenured. A full ordinal logistic model to predict the number of products based on log likelihoods with all factors yields a significant model fit ($P=0.0028$, loglikelihood=-9.06). After accounting for the number of participants and the years since the project ended, the only significant terms from the effect likelihood ratio tests were the percentage of minorities ($p=0.0337$) and percentage of postdoctoral fellows ($p=0.0216$). **Our findings suggest that working groups that incorporate a greater percentage of minorities and emerging scientists are more productive (Figure 20).** The latter supports our intuition that working groups possessing more non-tenured scientists are likely to feel a greater impetus for completing projects.

The finding of a relationship between minority representation and productivity is surprising and will require further investigation.

Figure 20: Cumulative logistic probability plot for number of products and percentage of minorities among working groups. The first bottom curve shows the probability attributed to zero products as the percentage of minorities varies. The distance between the top curve and top of the graph is the probability attributed to greater than 8 products. Note that as the percentage of minorities' increases (x-axis), the model gives more probability to higher numbers of products. At percentage of 40% most weight is given to products greater than 5.

10. How do NESCent supported interactions differ from more traditional collaborations and what factors drive these differences?

The “Science of Science Project” aims to improve the ways that NESCent promotes synthetic evolutionary science. The focus of the project is on the behaviors and attitudes of scientists towards collaboration, and how such behavior is changed as a result of NESCent support. The project results will provide NESCent with important information about the value of its programs in building communities and in creating a culture of collaboration.

Formative assessment for the “Science of Science Project” includes four programs: (1) working groups, (2) catalysis meetings, (3) post-doctoral scholars, and (4) informatics hackathons. Specifically, the protocol involves interviews and observations for each of the programs (which has been completed) followed by survey data collection (which is ongoing). Survey data focuses on the nature of interdisciplinary research, extent of collaboration, impact of NESCent participation, and generation of new knowledge. The plan is to continue gathering survey data from each of the four programs, which includes so far 27 out of 30 working groups, 7 out of 10 catalysis meetings, 4 out of 5 post-doctoral scholars, and 2 out of 4 informatics hackathons (Figure 21). A combination of internal survey responses,

demographics from NESCent’s administrative database, and variables gleaned from participant CVs forms the basis for our dataset. The deliverable for the formative assessment is an analysis, using a heierarchical linear model, of survey data highlighting what factors predict collaboration and novel interdisciplinary research within and across the programs.

Project	2009-2011		Meeting	Surveyed 2009-2010	Surveyed 2011 (so far)	Scheduled 2011 (so far)
	# Groups	# Participants	1st WG	9	7	1
Hackathons	2	55 (135 surveys)	2nd WG	10	1	3
Post-Doc Interviews	n/a	4	3rd WG	9	2	2
Catalysis Meetings	7	188	4th WG	3	0	4
Working Groups	27 (41 surveys)	392 (578 surveys)	Total WG	31	10	10
TOTAL	50	901	CM	4	3	5

Figure 21: Survey progress for the “Science of Science Project.” Data collection is ongoing and dependent on meeting scheduling and support cycles.

Assessing/Evaluating NESCent Education, Outreach and Communication

Education, Outreach and Communication at NESCent - What Do We Do?

The Education, Outreach and Communication (EOC) group at NESCent promotes effective teaching and learning of evolutionary science to diverse audiences and broadly communicates NESCent science.

EOC activities and initiatives are most effectively illustrated by viewing them within a framework of the audience(s) they serve. The table, below, summarizes our audiences and the specific activities and initiatives that serve them.

Audience	Activities/Initiatives
Education Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NABT Evolution Symposium and Teacher Workshop • Summer Workshop for High School Teachers • Darwin Day Roadshow • <i>Evolution in the News</i> Podcasts • NESCent Ambassador Program • Guest Lectures and Classroom Visits
Science Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Postdoc Professional Development Activities • NESCent Ambassador Program • Press Releases • NESCent Newsletter
General Public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Darwin Day Activities • Sponsorship of Public Talks, Science Cafés
Underrepresented Minorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SACNAS Conference Activities • <i>Undergraduate Diversity at Evolution</i> Travel Award Program • NESCent MSI Faculty Travel Award Program • MSI Guest Lecture Program

EOC Assessment - What Questions Are We Asking?

The general approach of NESCent's EOC group is to assess all of its activities and initiatives as thoroughly as possible, at multiple levels, although some EOC activities are inherently more assessable than others. The general questions being asked during EOC assessment, in ascending order of rigor, are:

1. How many people are we reaching? If we're providing resources to our audience(s), how much are we distributing?
2. Who are these individuals? Where are they from? What is their background?
3. How are the resources being used? How effective are they? How can they be improved?
4. What is the perceived value of our activities and initiatives? How likely would our audiences be to recommend them to colleagues?
5. What impact are we having on our audience? Are we improving their understanding of evolution or their ability to teach/communicate it effectively? Are the benefits only short term, or are there also long term impacts?
6. With respect to our outreach efforts to underrepresented minorities, do our efforts impact understanding of, or perceptions regarding evolution? Ultimately, will they result in greater numbers of underrepresented minorities pursuing research opportunities, graduate studies and careers in evolutionary science?

The primary level of assessment (which is analogous to the *Tier 1* assessment performed on NESCent Science initiatives), involves collection of quantitative data, such as head counts of participants/attendees at events, hits on NESCent's Education/Outreach website or numbers of CDs and resource collections distributed to teachers (question 1, above). These types of data are collected for virtually all EOC activities.

The next level of assessment would include demographic data associated with our participants (question 2, above). These data are still analogous to *Tier 1* assessment data, although for reasons that will be discussed below, they are not collected for all EOC activities.

More complex, still, are questions 3 and 4, which begin to examine use, efficacy and perceived value of EOC activities. These are analogous to *Tier 2* assessment, and as with the demographic data, not all EOC activities are assessable at this level.

The most complex and challenging questions (5 and 6, above) explore impact, sustainability, retention and long term benefits of our activities. These questions are the most valuable in many ways, they also represent some of the greatest challenges with respect to collection.

EOC Assessment - What Are The Challenges?

As mentioned previously, some EOC activities are inherently more assessable than others, and several unique challenges exist with respect to assessment of EOC activities. The two most notable challenges are:

1. EOC activities are often large, open-to-the-public events, which can make them inherently difficult to assess via traditional methods (such as participant surveys). In the absence of the ability to distribute surveys or collect any direct or indirect feedback on EOC activities, we are often left with only the first level (question 1) information.
2. Activities designed to improve the quality of evolution education (e.g., teacher workshops, the NABT Evolution Symposium), change perceptions (e.g., Darwin Day activities) or increase interest in evolution graduate study/careers (e.g., minority outreach efforts) all require long-term (several year) follow-up in order to be properly assessed.

Nonetheless, whenever possible, we collect survey data (demographics, efficacy, perceived utility, etc.) at time of activity and at follow-up times. Additionally, we are always collecting anecdotal reports and data, which are used for both formative and summative assessment. And, as mentioned previously, for virtually all EOC activities we collect quantitative data (head counts at activities, CDs distributed, etc.)

EOC Assessment - Some Representative Data

The representative data that follow give a snapshot of the types of questions we are able to ask.

The NABT Evolution Symposium

The first set demonstrates some of the quantitative and demographic data we collect from participants of the Evolution Symposium we organize each year at the National Association of Biology Teachers (NABT) Conference, in conjunction with the American Institute of Biological Sciences (AIBS).

Attendance at Previous Symposia			
Other Symposia Attended		Number of other symposia attended	
2004	20	One	11
2005	15	Two	3
2006	13	Three	10
Total	49		

States Represented by Respondents		
AR - 1	KY - 2	NY - 7
CA - 4	LA - 1	OK - 3
CO - 1	MA - 3	OR - 1
CT - 4	ME - 1	PA - 3
FL - 2	MI - 1	SC - 2
GA - 3	MN - 1	TN - 2
IA - 3	MO - 1	VT - 3
ID - 1	MS - 1	WA - 3
IL - 9	NC - 8	WI - 1
IN - 1	NE - 1	Alberta, Canada - 2
KS - 2	NJ - 1	Ontario, Canada - 1
Total: 78 people, 31/50 states		

- What level do you teach? (85 respondents)
 - Middle school: 1 (1%)
 - High school: 42 (49%)
 - Two year college: 21 (25%)
 - Four year college: 15 (18%)
 - Other: 6 (7%)

- How long have you been teaching? (85 respondents)
 - Pre-service: 2 (2%)
 - 1 year: 1 (1%)
 - 2-5 years: 8 (9%)
 - 6-10 years: 14 (16%)
 - 11-20 years: 23(28%)
 - Greater than 20 years: 23 (28%)
 - Retired/Other: 14 (16%)

We have been co-organizing this annual symposium with AIBS at the NABT conference since NESCent's first full year of existence in 2005, and have been collecting demographic data such as these since 2006. Our data show indicate that we typically average anywhere from 70-100

participants each year, and as indicated from the figures above, they typically represent a wide geographic range and diverse level of instruction (K-12, undergraduate, ISE). These data help us determine appropriate topics for our symposia, and provide future symposium speakers with a better sense of how to gauge their presentations appropriately.

We have also recently formed an NABT Evolution Symposium Teacher Advisory Board (NESTAB), which consists of nine teachers/instructors who have attended at least one symposium and/or associated teacher workshop in the past. The NESTAB provides input on past symposia and workshops, and suggestions for future topics. The NABT Evolution Symposium organizing committee (consisting of AIBS and NESCent EOC staff) is continually exploring ways to increase the utility of NESTAB as a component of our assessment/evaluation.

Undergraduate Diversity at Evolution

Each year since 2008, NESCent EOC staff have collaborated with Drs. Scott Edwards (Harvard) and Rich Kliman (Cedar Crest College) to bring up to 25 undergraduates from diverse backgrounds to the annual Evolution (SSE/SSB/ASN) conference, where they present their own research, receive mentoring and career guidance and participate in social and networking activities.

At the completion of the conference, both the students and mentors are surveyed to collect demographics and assessment data on the perceived utility of the activities. We have data from all three years in which NESCent has participated (2008-2010), and some representative data are shown below, starting with student demographics:

Demographic data from the mentors:

1) Which of the following best describes you?

Graduate student	2	11%
Postdoc	5	28%
Faculty member	10	56%
Other	1	6%

2) How did you find out about this program (Please select all that apply)

From my professor/research advisor	0	0%
From a friend/colleague	9	50%
From the EvolDir listserv	6	33%
Other	4	22%

People may select more than one checkbox, so percentages may add up to more than 100%.

Below are data on perceived utility and efficacy from undergraduate participants in the *Undergraduate Diversity at Evolution* program:

5) Poster session (at which you presented your own poster)

Extremely valuable/enjoyable	33	87%
Valuable/enjoyable	4	11%
Neutral/No opinion	0	0%
Not valuable/enjoyable	1	3%
Don't include this in the future	0	0%

7) "Futures" Talk/Panel discussion

Extremely valuable/enjoyable	12	32%
Valuable/enjoyable	11	29%
Neutral/No opinion	12	32%
Not valuable/enjoyable	3	8%
Don't include this in the future	0	0%

8) Mentoring

12) Participating in the Undergraduate Diversity program was valuable for me.

14) I have a better understanding of how a scientific conference works because of my participation in this program.

16) I am likely/more likely to apply to graduate programs in evolution and pursue careers in evolution because of my participation in this program.

These data give us a better sense of who the student participants are and which activities are beneficial to them, and importantly, how participation in this program benefits them overall and

changes their perspectives and attitudes with respect to studying and pursuing careers in evolutionary science.

In addition, we survey the scientists who serve as mentors to the undergraduate participants of the *Undergraduate Diversity at Evolution* program. The following are representative data from those surveys:

14) I would recommend participating as a mentor in the Undergraduate Diversity program to my friends/colleagues

15) I am enthusiastic/more enthusiastic about mentoring undergraduates as a result of participating in this program

These data not only demonstrate that this is a positive experience for the mentors, but help us in our efforts to recruit future mentors, many of whom are young scientists themselves (e.g., NESCent postdocs), so the mentoring activities serve as valuable professional development activities for them.

NESCent Summer Workshop for High School Teachers

Starting in 2009, the EOC group offered a three-day summer workshop for high school teachers on effective teaching of evolution. (See <http://www.nescent.org/courses/2009/eogsummer.php> and <https://www.nescent.org/courses/2010/eogsummer/index.php> for more information.) This workshop was designed to provide evolution content, pedagogy, hands-on activities to be used by participating teachers in their classrooms and resources to assist their teaching.

Both years that we have offered this workshop we have collected detailed survey data both at the end of the workshop and at 6-month or 1-year follow up timepoints.

The following are data collected at the end of the workshop:

The following are results from a six-month follow up survey distributed to participants of the workshop surveyed above. These data demonstrate our ability to determine utility and efficacy

after workshop participants have had an opportunity to implement resources and activities acquired during our workshop.

1) Were you able to use things you learned/gained from the workshop in your teaching this semester.

4) Thinking back on the evolution content that was covered in the workshop, how useful was that to you this semester?

5) How useful were the classroom activities that were introduced in the workshop (e.g., "The Great Clade Race", Avida-ED and Aipotu online evolution simulations, the "Deep Time" walk)?

8) Have you continued to use the Workshop Resource Page (http://www.nescent.org/courses/2009/eogsummer_resources_2009.php) since the workshop ended?

Overall, these data give us a good indication of how workshop participants felt about the utility of the content, tools and resources they received during the course of the workshop. We feel that

the 6-month follow up data are particularly valuable, as anecdotal reports have suggested that it is not until teachers are back in the classroom that they can properly assess how useful a workshop has been.

Ultimately, we feel the most meaningful data for these types of workshops are the following:

9) Overall, I am:

10) Overall, this course:

11) I would recommend this workshop to a colleague.

In particular, the fact that all respondents would recommend the workshop to colleagues demonstrates in a powerful way that this is a valuable experience for teachers.

The Evolution in the News Program

The Evolution in the News program is a collaborative effort between Understanding Evolution and NESCent. This freely available resource is designed to engage students in current, socially relevant research in evolutionary biology. We received an NSF CCLI grant to assess and improve the program to ensure that it is effective in conveying evolutionary concepts, engaging for students, and useful for educators while identifying new strategies for dissemination and classroom use. The UNC Evaluation, Assessment and Policy (EvAP) group worked with the program staff to develop an online pre/post-survey style assessment tool.

The results from this initial assessment of the program were very promising. In addition to the success of the program as a teaching tool, we gained insight into how the program is used. We continue to assess the program in individual classrooms, and implement the small changes suggested by the results of these assessments to increase value and dissemination.

NESCent Short Courses, Workshops and Symposia

Since NESCent's initial funding we have offered a wide variety of short courses, workshops and symposia focusing on evolutionary science, evolutionary informatics and evolution education. These have been offered to a diverse audience, including K-12 students and teachers, undergraduates, graduate students, postdocs and faculty. The table that follows summarizes the short courses and workshops that have been offered, to date.

Course/Workshop Name	Instructor(s)/ Speaker(s)	Start Date	End Date	No. of Students/ Participants
NABT 2005 Evolution Symposium - Evolution and the Environment	Anthony Baranosky, Andrew Blaustein, Jonathan Losos, Kenneth Olsen, Stephen Palumbi, Barbara Schaal, Pam Soltis	10-07-2005	10-07-2005	~100
NABT 2006 Evolution Symposium - Macroevolution: Evolution	Philip Gingerich, Scott Hodges,	10-14-2006	10-14-2006	~100

Above the Species Level	David Jablonski, Nicole King, Jeff Levinton, Nipam Patel			
Rashkis Elementary School of Chapel Hill: 5th Grade Class	Joseph Fail	04-26-2007	04-26-2007	28
Computational Phyloinformatics Summer Course 2007	William Piel	07-09-2007	07-19-2007	31
NABT 2007 Evolution Symposium - Evolution: Applications in Human Health and Populations	George Armelagos, Carlos Bustamante, Mark Lipsitch, Sandra Romero-Steiner, Sandra Soo-Jin Lee, David Sloan Wilson	12-01-2007	12-01-2007	~100
PAEMST Systematics Workshop	Kristin Jenkins, Sonja Scheffer, Brian Wiegmann	04-29-2008	04-29-2008	~30
Tools for Teaching Evolution	John Jungck, Jory Weintraub	05-29-2008	05-29-2008	18
Evolutionary Biology and Ontologies Workshop	Paula Mabee, Todd Vision	06-20-2008	06-20-2008	Unknown
Teaching An Elementary Story of Life	Joseph Fail	07-14-2008	07-18-2008	10
Computational Phyloinformatics Summer Course 2008	Hilmar Lapp , William Piel	07-24-2008	08-04-2008	39
NABT 2008: Biogeography Symposium	Joel Cracraft , Frank Fontanella , Kathryn Perez	10-07-2008	10-07-2008	Unknown
NABT 2008 Evolution Symposium - Illuminating Biology: An Evolutionary Perspective	Bob Blankenship, Joram Piatigorsky, Goerg Striedter, Trisha Wittkopp	10-16-2008	10-16-2008	~100
Using Free, Intuitive Software to Explore Mysteries of Evolutionary History in the High School Biology Classroom (at NABT 2008)	Jeff McKinnon, Bob Kuzoff	10-16-2008	10-16-2008	~15
NABT 2008 Evolution Symposium Education Resources Workshop	Sam Donovan , Kristin Jenkins , Brian Wiegmann	10-17-2008	10-17-2008	~20
Metadata Architectures and Applications	Jane Greenberg	11-17-2008	11-17-2008	Unknown

Ontology workshop at SICB 2009	Paula Mabee, Todd Vision	01-05-2009	01-05-2009	Unknown
Evolution 2009: A Workshop for Educators	Alex Glass, Kristin Jenkins, Jenny Tung, Jory Weintraub	06-29-2009	07-01-2009	15
An Introduction to Meta-analysis in Ecology and Evolutionary Biology	Jessica Gurevitch, Marc Lajeunesse, Kerrie Mengersen	07-06-2009	07-10-2009	22
Computational Phyloinformatics Summer Course 2009	Pedro Fernandes, Hilmar Lapp, William Piel	07-09-2009	07-19-2009	16
2009 GMOD Summer School - Americas	David Clements	07-16-2009	07-19-2009	34
2009 GMOD Summer School - Europe	David Clements	08-03-2009	08-06-2009	37
NABT 2009 Evolution Symposium - Evolution in Extreme Environments	Cynthia Beall, Steve Haddock, William Jefferey, Jody Deming	11-13-2009	11-13-2009	~100
NABT 2009 Evolution Symposium Education Resources Workshop	Kristin Jenkins, Susan Musante	11-14-2009	11-14-2009	~25
Applied Phylogenetics Workshop	Todd Vision	03-06-2010	03-13-2010	Unknown
Regression and Classification Tree Workshop	Richard Cutler	04-12-2010	04-14-2010	Unknown
2009 GMOD Summer School - Americas	David Clements	05-06-2010	05-09-2010	Unknown
Comparative Methods and Macroevolution In R Summer Short Course	Mike Alfaro, Luke Harmon	06-17-2010	06-21-2010	Unknown
Evolution 2010: A Workshop for Educators	Alex Glass, Kristin Jenkins, Robin Smith, Jory Weintraub	06-21-2010	06-23-2010	15

Paleobiology Database Intensive Workshop in Analytical Methods	John Alroy, Gene Hunt, Tom Olszewski, David Polly, Pete Wagner	07-07-2010	08-10-2010	Unknown
Computational Phyloinformatics Summer Course 2010 – Shenzhen, China	William Piel, Rutger Vos	07-07-2010	08-10-2010	Unknown
NABT 2010 Evolution Symposium – Molecular Insights into Classic Examples of Evolution	Edmund “Butch” Brodie, Sean Carroll, Hopi Hoekstra, Allen Rodrigo	11-05-2010	11-05-2010	~100
NABT 2010 Evolution Symposium Education Resources Workshop	Kristin Jenkins, Susan Musante	11-06-2010	11-06-2010	~25
2011 GMOD Spring Training	Dave Clements	03-04-2010	03-12-2010	25

Summary, Conclusions and Future Directions

In summary, while some EOC programs and activities are more “assessable” than others, all are designed with evaluation and assessment in mind. Our general approach is to collect quantitative data for all of our activities measuring how many people we are reaching. Whenever possible, we augment this with demographic data, as well as data on perceived utility and efficacy.

Our conclusion from these assessment efforts is that EOC programs and activities are reaching diverse audiences at all levels of scholarship with positive results/outcomes. Our assessment efforts, both formative and summative, are used to make changes to EOC programs and activities when necessary to ensure that we continue to have a positive impact on the audiences and communities we serve.

Moving forward, we will continue to explore more rigorous assessment approaches. When possible (such as with the NESCent Ambassador program, which recently received NSF support through the EAGER mechanism) we will engage external evaluation/assessment groups to further strengthen assessment of EOC activities. Ultimately, we hope to be able to better assess sustainability, retention and long term impacts and benefits of our activities, although these will always represent a challenge, given the distributed/public nature of many EOC activities.

Assessing NESCent's informatics programs

The mission of NESCent's informatics programs

NESCent's informatics programs have a two-pronged mission: (1) providing its sponsored scientists with the consulting, collaboration tools, software, or hardware resources they need to accomplish their scientific goals and (2) strengthening the informatics capacity for synthetic evolutionary biology in the greater community.

As with EOC, there are challenges in assessing the impact of the Center's informatics investments, since there is great variety in the intended impacts among the different activities. We are in the early phases of implementing our assessment framework for informatics, and so here we attempt only to provide an overview of the kinds of questions we hope to answer, and some examples of the kinds of data that are at hand. The initiatives of relevance include the following.

Sponsored science support

- Off-the-shelf collaboration tools and basic IT support infrastructure
- Consulting and custom software solutions

Capacity building for community-driven software development

- Informatics-oriented courses
- "Summer of Code" Internships
- Hackathons
- Sponsorship of the iEvoBio conference

Cyberinfrastructure initiatives

- GMOD User Support
- Phenoscape
- The Dryad Data Repository and DataONE

The overarching questions we seek to address are:

- Have we enabled our sponsored scientists to do synthesis?
- Is there uptake of the technologies we have developed and promoted?
- Have we strengthened the community of open source evoinformatics?
- Are we fostering culture change around greater data sharing?

Have we enabled our sponsored scientists to do synthesis?

Levels of support

The pie chart to the right shows the level of support provided on a per-project basis. The data includes working groups, catalysis meetings, postdocs, short-term and sabbatical scholars. Bear in mind that custom software development is only provided in special cases for catalysis meetings and short-term visitors. Overall, 14% of projects require non-routine consultation with informatics staff, and another 14% require custom software development of one form or another.

No support provided (e.g. some meetings in Yr1)

Off-the-shelf support only (e.g. wiki, mailing list, High Performance Computing)

Consulting

Custom software development

Off-the-shelf IT support and consulting

We have a number of sources of data that can be used to assess satisfaction with off-the-shelf IT support and to judge the extent of reuse of the off-the-shelf resources provided. From surveys of visitors, 77% of respondents rate the IT support as a 4 or 5 out of 5, indicating overall satisfaction. From usage logs of the 86 wikis provided to working groups, there is a mean of 750 edits and 3 MB of (directly input) content. From reviewing records of the entry interviews with resident scholars (primarily postdocs and sabbatical scholars), the most common request is for information about High Performance (HPC) resources. We have been able to meet user demand for HPC resources in nearly all cases. We have no effective means at present to assess our IT consulting services.

Custom software development

Custom software development is tailored to the scientific objectives of the sponsored scientists. Thus, there is no 'typical' project, though a number of projects have involved development of a database to support the synthesis of data from a working group. Many sponsored scientists are also themselves software developers, and produce software as part of their project with the direct involvement of informatics staff. While we make an effort to track software products wholly developed by sponsored scientists, here we are concerned with those products that required non-negligible investment of informatics staff effort.

In assessing these projects, we need a framework that acknowledges that their goals vary, since they are driven by scientific imperatives unique to each project. Nonetheless, we find it instructive to systematically examine a common set of vital statistics for each informatics project after sponsored science support ceases. Has there been a published article describing the product, and if so has it been cited? Have there been views/downloads? Have data been updated or new versions of software released? Is the project continuing to recruit new developers community? Are the products currently being used by the scientists for whom they were developed? There are no natural baselines for these comparison, and the relevance of each question differs from project to project. Nonetheless, this provides a useful framework for evaluating the outcome of each project with respect to both its original scientific goals and

NESCent’s larger objectives with respect to informatics capacity building. Knowing how each of these products is now being used, maintained, or built upon, allows the informatics staff to better predict what returns on investment we are likely to achieve for different kinds of custom software projects.

Some vital statistics are presented below for a representative set of projects. Green indicates “Yes”, orange indicates “No”, and gray indicates “Not Applicable”. For example, taking the first row, Chado NatDiv is a database schema for natural genetic diversity that was developed to support particular sponsored science project beginning in 2006. A paper describing the schema is currently slated for a special online issue of the journal Database. Since it is still in production, that article has not yet received citations. Interestingly, Chado NatDiv is not currently being used by the sponsored scientist for whom it was originally developed (“Used by SS” column) but it is released as a core component of the Chado database and has been adopted by several large GMOD users (“Used outside SS”). The codebase in Sourceforge continues to be improved on a regular basis (“New code”). Since it is not a database instance itself, it is not possible to measure the number of years since data have been updated (“Yrs data stasis”) and since it is part of a larger codebase, the number of downloads is not meaningful. Taken as a whole, this suggests a mixed outcome, in which custom software development produced something of continued value to a larger community while at the same time not serving the immediate needs of a sponsored science project.

	Yrs since support	Published	Citations	Used by SS	Used outside SS	New code	Yrs data stasis	Downloads
Chado NatDiv	5	Green	Orange	Orange	Green	Green	Gray	Gray
GeoPhylobuilder	4	Green	Green	Green	Green	Orange	Gray	594
Max Size DB	2	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	2	Gray
Primate Life Hist DB	<1	Green	Orange	Green	Orange	Gray	Gray	Gray
Mammal Feed DB	<1	Green	Green	Green	Orange	Gray	Gray	Gray

A very different kind of product is illustrated in the second row. Geophylobuilder is an application for viewing phylogenetic trees within standard GIS software with the tips mapped to points on a landscape. The 2008 publication describing the software has garnered 11 citations (according to Google Scholar on 05-23-2011). It is being used by the sponsored scientist who initially proposed the software (and who contributed substantially to its development). It has been downloaded by hundreds of users and there is evidence of its continued use. However, the software has not been actively updated for two years.

The following rows show examples of database projects of varying vitality. The Maximum Size Database was intended as more of a public face to the synthetic data set compiled by a working group, while the Primate Life History Database was intended as a resource primarily for the working group participants themselves to collaborate, and the Mammalian Feeding Database was intended as an archival database to be prototyped among working group members and then opened as an archive for contributions from a wider community of relevant domain scientists.

We recognize that this list of vital statistics is incomplete. Perhaps most importantly, some, but not all, projects have served as the basis for follow-on activities, such as the recent success of an ABI proposal to further development of the Mammalian Feeding DB, that was made possible by the success of the prototype.

Have we strengthened the community of open source evoinformatics?

NESCent has several projects and activities that promote human capacity building in open source informatics. In addition to the informatics-related courses (reported elsewhere), NESCent hosts 6-12 summer interns each year through the Google Summer of Code (GSoC) program, organizes annual hackathons in areas ripe for collaborative development, and has launched the iEvoBio conference as a satellite to the annual Evolution meeting.

One measure of success with these initiatives is the extent to which new people are recruited to contribute to open source projects, and evidence of their sustained involvement. The histogram at right shows the pattern for the GSoC program. Of the 32 students the program has supported through 2010, twelve are still active in their respective projects, five have gone on to become mentors of NESCent GSoC projects in subsequent years, two have subsequently participated in hackathons, and one has become a NESCent postdoc. Note that we do not have comparative data (i.e. for “Still active” and “GSoC mentor”) from other mentoring organizations. Also, while it does not reflect on the ongoing participation of the students, it is worth pointing out that the outcomes of the GSoC projects were well-represented at the inaugural iEvoBio meeting in Portland in 2010 (for which there were 308 registrants).

We can also monitor the vital statistics that are relevant to cyberinfrastructure software projects, as we did above for sponsored science. In the table below, orange again represents “No”, green “Yes”, and gray “Not applicable”. For example, the Phylobase package, a shared library used by many other phylogenetics packages in R, was first conceived at a hackathon in 2007. There is no publication describing the software, though there is a conference poster available from Nature Precedings (doi:10.1038/npre.2008.2126.1). It has been widely adopted, and the code is still being maintained, within the R phylogenetics community. We estimate there to be hundreds of users/downloads based on mailing list traffic. The current list of sixteen developers and administrators on R-forge includes several who have been recruited since the hackathon. Follow-on activities (not shown) include a 2008 Google Summer of Code project which added new tree plotting functionality.

	Launched	Published	Cited	Data reuse	Adoption	Latest code	Latest data	Downloads	New developers
R Phylobase	2007 (Hack.)	Orange	Orange	Gray	Green	2011	Gray	100s	Green
PhyloWidget	2007 (GSoC)	Green	Green	Gray	Green	2009	Gray	100s	Orange

Another important goal that is subtly visible within the vital stats is the synergy between sponsored science and cyberinfrastructure software projects. The R Phylobase package grew out of a hackathon, but the hackathon itself was proposed in a whitepaper submitted by a group of NESCent postdocs. Similarly,

the Chado NatDiv module discussed above grew out of sponsored science, but now has been adopted within the GMOD community.

Is there uptake of technologies we have promoted?

In measuring uptake of new technology, we consider the unique goals of each. For example, Phenoscape is a project that grew out of a working group and evolved into a collaborative ABI grant. It is a demonstration and test project for the utility of using ontologies to link knowledge about phenotypes trapped within the evolutionary biology literature to knowledge about model organism genetics. Core to the project is the idea that the community of scientists who have deep knowledge about the systematics and anatomy of organisms need to be directly engaged in the development of the ontologies and software that leverage that knowledge. Phenoscape cannot yet boast software with hundreds or thousands of users, and at this phase, it is more appropriate to look at measures community engagement, such as the number of scientists who have contributed to the development of Anatomy and Taxonomy Ontologies, have used Phenoscape tools to annotate phenotype data from the systematics literature, have attended one of the three workshops held at various conferences, have participated in software testing, and students who have done internships of one form or another on the project (<https://www.phenoscape.org/wiki/Contributors>)

Measures of community engagement in Phenoscape

- Anatomy Ontology contributors: 25
- Taxonomy Ontology contributors: 11
- Data contributors: 10
- Workshop Participants: >75
- Software testing: >30
- Students: 13

In addition, there is sufficient interest in the broader community to have recently led to the launch of a Phenotype Ontology Research Coordination Network (<http://phenotypercn.org>).

NESCent has also played a role in promoting GMOD as a standard-based technology suite for management of genomic data for a wider community. The GMOD help desk based at NESCent (funded since 2007 by the NIH), has been tracking project statistics at http://gmod.org/wiki/Project_Statistics. As shown by the two charts below, growth in users of the gmod.org documentation pages, and GMOD-related mailing list traffic, have been substantial. In the case of the Gbrowse mailing list, traffic has grown several-fold over the last four years. This reflects the fact that there are estimated to be now over 200 new installations of Gbrowse per month.

Are we fostering culture change around greater data sharing?

NESCent's flagship initiative for data sharing has been incubating the Dryad Data Repository, and the involvement of Dryad within the NSF funded DataONE network. As of May 2011, the Dryad repository currently has nearly 700 data packages associated with articles in over 75 journals. A relevant measure of success for Dryad is the level of commitment from partner journals. This can take three forms: Dryad encourages journals to require public archiving of data underlying findings in the articles they publish (e.g. through adoption of the Joint Data Archiving Policy), to integrate submission of data to Dryad with submission of the manuscript (making data archiving low burden and encouraging compliance), and materially contributing to the sustainability of the repository (e.g. through a commitment to be a subscriber when the repository transitions to a service mode). The table on the next page lists the involvement of journals in each of these three categories. An "A" in the subscription column indicates that the journal has indicated that they are committed to subscribe to Dryad's proposed subscription Plan A, which charges journals based on the total number of research papers published annually. As of the beginning of May, there were 15 journals that required data archiving (not all through the influence of Dryad, but the majority), 20 journals that integrate manuscript with data submission (or for which integration is in process), and 9 journals that have agreed to be charter Plan A subscribers. These numbers are continuing to grow.

Journal	Society or publisher	Archiving rqmnt	Submission integration	Subscriber
American Naturalist	ASN	Y	Y	A
Evolution	SSE	Y	Y	A
Systematic Biology	SSB	Y	Y	A
Molecular Biology & Evolution	SMBE	Y	-	A
Heredity	The Genetics Soc.	Y	In progress	A
Journal of Heredity	AGA	-	Y	A
Paleobiology / J. of Paleontology	Paleontology Society	Y	In progress	A
Ecological Monographs	ESA	Y	In progress	A
Journal of Evolutionary Biology	ESEB	Y	Y	A
Molecular Ecology / MER	Wiley-Blackwell	Y	Y	-
Biological J. Linnean Society	Linnean Soc. London	-	Y	-
Evolutionary Applications	Wiley-Blackwell	Y	Y	-
Integrative & Comparative Biology	SICB	-	In progress	-
BMC Ecology / BMC Evolution	Springer/BMC	Y	In progress	-
BMJ Open	BMJ	-	In progress	
PLoS Biology	PLoS	-	In progress	-
J Fish Wildlife Management	Fish & Wildlife Service	Y	In progress	-
Journal of Ecology	British Ecological Soc.	-	In progress	-
21 journals		15	20	9

Another way to measure the success of our data sharing efforts is the extent to which Dryad data is being reused. Insufficient time has accumulated to analyze this rigorously, but download statistics are already high (greater than 30) for dozens of datasets. Disappointingly, only 10% of NESCent publications have associated data in Dryad, which is something we have been working to improve; at the same time, datasets associated with NESCent projects are among the most highly downloaded (and will likely be the most highly cited) datasets in the repository. Interestingly, this includes some of the datasets that are at the core of sponsored science software projects, such as the Maximum Body Size Database ([doi:10.1073/pnas.0806314106](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0806314106)) and the Primate Life History Database ([doi:10.5061/dryad.8682](https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.8682)). One dataset submitted in 2009 by former NESCent postdoc Amy Zanne and her collaborators ([doi:10.5061/dryad.234](https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.234)) has already been downloaded over 800 times. It is likely that many of these downloads are for educational, rather than research purposes, something not easily tracked by standard metrics (i.e. citations).

Through the work of NESCent/DataONE postdoc Heather Piwowar, several studies are ongoing to study the evolving culture of data archiving and reuse, and in particular to assess the role of data archiving infrastructure and data archiving mandates. One study aims to understand the value of archived data by tracking the reuse of 100 datasets from each of 10 data repositories. The questions include:

- How often is data from repositories used in the published literature?
- What is the distribution of use across datasets and time?
- Who reuses data?
- Are investigators who reuse repository datasets similar to investigators who deposit data?
- What is data reused for?
- How similar are studies that reuse data to studies that deposit data?

This study received an ASIS&T Elfreda A. Chatman Research Proposal Award, and results will be available in early 2012. More information at <http://researchremix.wordpress.org>.

A second study examines the impact of journal archiving policies by surveying all corresponding authors of all articles over three years (starting Fall 2010) for 48 journals in 3 categories: those that have adopted the Joint Data Archiving Policy of the Dryad Consortium, other ecology and evolution journals, and an extra-disciplinary control set. The questions of interest are:

- How do authors' attitudes, experiences, and practices around public data archiving change when the journals they publish in adopt mandatory data archiving policies?
- Are changes specific to the journals that implement the policies, or do they extend to other journals in the same subfield?

More information on this study is available at <http://studyonimpactofjournaldatapolicies.wordpress.com>.

Future Directions

Many questions about impact and role of NESCent remain for the future. These outstanding lines inquiry are in part fueled by the previous analyses and by new challenges facing the center. Many of these present data collection or analytical barriers that must be overcome. Particularly profitable will be emphasizing collaborations with those in information science and scientometrics. Our assessment program has also been enriched by utilizing a synthetic approach borrowing techniques from strengths in evolutionary and biological sciences with emphasis on quantification and analytical methods. Our future program will continue to leverage these assets. Below we highlight some outstanding questions regarding NESCent assessment that we hope to address in the next year.

- Do varying NESCent support models produce outputs proportional to their support, participants, and duration?
- Does NESCent produce more publications with greater impact per NSF dollar compared to traditional research institutes and departments?
- Does the impact of NESCent publications and press releases disseminate across audiences? This is a collaboration with Jason Priem at UNC utilizing a variety of metrics that draw on the growth of new, online scholarly tools that can measure the rapid impact of scholarship.
- Does demographic diversity of a working group impact its scholarly impact?
- Do emerging and experienced participants interact in the creation of NESCent products?
- Does NESCent foster a culture of open data access across the broader scientific community through increased generation, availability, and utilization of such data?
- Are participants in NESCent activities more successful in receiving future funding?
- Do NESCent postdoctoral fellows have greater career success?
- Do research themes and collaborations originating at NESCent persist after removal of NESCent support?
- Does NESCent induce shifts in disciplinary trends (i.e. emergence, convergence, and/or combination) within science?
- Does NESCent stimulate synthetic activity in the broader scientific community?
- Does NESCent create a foundation of scientific tools that promote analyses, interpretation, and visualization of complex data sets vital to synthetic science?
- Does NESCent offer internal and foster external opportunities for the development of skills needed for continued synthesis?
- Does NESCent increase access to resources and information to enhance evolutionary science education?
- Does NESCent increase participation of underrepresented minorities in evolutionary science?
- Does NESCent communication to the general public result in increased access to and understanding of the scientific process, evolutionary science, and synthetic science?